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- ✓ IJTIMOY FANLAR

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HYPOTHYROIDISM IS A PROBLEM OF THE XXI ERA

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Annotation. *The article reflects issues of epidemiology, classification, and clinical picture of hypothyroidism. The incidence of hypothyroidism increases significantly with age. The most common form is primary hypothyroidism, caused by a pathological process in the thyroid gland itself. Secondary or tertiary hypothyroidism is caused by insufficient secretion of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), or thyrotropin-releasing hormone. The article discusses the main causes of primary and secondary hypothyroidism. The most common cause of primary hypothyroidism is autoimmune thyroiditis, which can develop either separately or simultaneously with other autoimmune diseases, as part of polyglandular syndrome. Changes in thyroid status as a consequence of adverse side reactions when using a number of drugs deserve special attention. Questions have been raised about the mechanisms of development of thyroid failure as a result of adverse side reactions when using a number of drugs (lithium preparations, iodine-containing compounds, tyrosine kinase inhibitors, etc.).*

Keywords: *hypothyroidism, autoimmune thyroiditis, TSH, thyroid hormones, drug-induced hypothyroidism, replacement therapy, levothyroxine.*

ГИПОТИРЕОЗ – ПРОБЛЕМА XXI ЭПОХИ

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Аннотация. В статье отражены вопросы эпидемиологии, классификации и клиники гипотиреоза. Заболеваемость гипотиреозом значительно увеличивается с возрастом. Наиболее распространенной формой является первичный гипотиреоз, вызванный патологическим процессом в самой щитовидной железе. Вторичный или третичный гипотиреоз вызван недостаточной секрецией тиреотропного гормона (ТТГ) или тиреотропин-рилизинг-гормона. В статье рассмотрены основные причины первичного и вторичного гипотиреоза. Наиболее частой причиной первичного гипотиреоза является аутоиммунный тиреоидит, который может развиваться как отдельно, так и одновременно с другими аутоиммунными заболеваниями, в рамках полигландулярного синдрома. Особого внимания заслуживают изменения тиреоидного статуса как следствие побочных реакций при применении ряда препаратов. Поднимаются вопросы о механизмах развития тиреоидной недостаточности в результате побочных реакций при применении ряда лекарственных средств (препаратов лития, йодсодержащих соединений, ингибиторов тирозинкиназ и др.).

Ключевые слова: гипотиреоз, аутоиммунный тиреоидит, ТТГ, гормоны щитовидной железы, лекарственный гипотиреоз, заместительная терапия, левотироксин

Introduction. Hypothyroidism is one of the most common diseases of the endocrine system. Despite the well-studied etiology, pathogenesis and simple diagnosis, in some cases the disease remains unrecognized for a long time, which is due to the slow increase in thyroid insufficiency and, accordingly, the severity of the clinical picture. The biological action of thyroid hormones is very diverse: by activating the transcription of numerous genes, they participate in the regulation of basic physiological processes in the body, so their deficiency can manifest itself in a wide variety of clinical manifestations and symptoms and imitate diseases of almost all body systems. Interestingly, hypothyroidism is the first endocrine disease for which replacement therapy was used. The first description of hypothyroidism was made by W. Gall in 1873 [1]. Later, V. Ordomb proposed the term “myxedema” (myxa - mucus, oidema - swelling, edema; Greek) - mucous swelling of the skin and subcutaneous tissue (Fig. 1). Nowadays, this term is used to characterize the most severe forms of thyroid insufficiency. This is one of the common diseases of the thyroid gland: the prevalence, according to various studies, ranges from 0.2 to 3.7% and depends on age, gender, and level of iodine consumption [2, 3]. The annual incidence of primary hypothyroidism is 3.5 per 1 thousand women and 0.6 per 1 thousand men. The incidence of hypothyroidism increases significantly with age. In the age population over 60 years, taking into account subclinical forms, it can reach 6–12% of cases, more often in women [4, 5]. The Framingham Study found hypothyroidism (TSH > 10 mU/L) in 5.9% of women and 2.4% of men over 60 years of age [6]. Primary hypothyroidism is much more common (95%), caused by a pathological process in the thyroid gland (TG) itself [4, 7]. Thyroid pathology can be detected from birth (congenital hypothyroidism) in the presence of thyroid embryopathy (agenesis, hypogenesis, dystopia) or congenital failure of enzymatic systems involved in the biosynthesis of thyroid hormones. The cause of congenital hypothyroidism may be gene mutations that lead to disturbances in the anlage, migration, and differentiation of the thyroid gland; defects in the biosynthesis of thyroid hormones (TTF1, TTF2, PAX-8, NIS, TPO, iodotyrosine deiodinase gene) [8]. In adults, the most common cause of primary hypothyroidism is autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT), the prevalence of which, according to various studies, despite some differences in gender, age, race and iodine intake, reaches about 5% among the population [7, 9, 10]. The natural pattern of development of AIT is a gradual decrease in thyroid function to overt hypothyroidism with a progression rate of about 2–4% per year [9]. It should be remembered that AIT can develop either separately or simultaneously with other autoimmune diseases,

for example, as part of polyglandular syndrome [10]. Other causes of hypothyroidism due to destruction of the thyroid gland include thyroidectomy, radioactive iodine therapy, external irradiation during radiation therapy of malignant neoplasms outside the thyroid gland. It is always necessary to remember that the persistent nature of hypothyroidism can be judged no earlier than after 6 months. after similar interventions [11–13]. After thyroidectomy or a significant part of it, the operated patient (ultimate subtotal resection) develops postoperative hypothyroidism, the likelihood of which is determined by the purpose and scope of the operation. After hemithyroidectomy, the incidence of hypothyroidism ranges from 5 to 40% and depends on the period of time that has passed since surgery. It has been shown that in 67–90% of patients, thyroid insufficiency is observed after 12 months. after surgery [11, 12]. Disorders of thyroid function in response to exposure to external and internal ionizing radiation, in terms of the mechanism of their development and clinical manifestations, differ from thyroid hypofunction of other origins. In particular, post-radiation hypothyroidism can develop in the long term after irradiation (6–7 years), which requires an appropriate assessment of thyroid function over time. In these cases, hypothyroidism can occur with significantly lower doses of thyroid radiation (9.0–15.0 Gy) than with the use of radioactive iodine for therapeutic purposes (35–40 Gy) [13].

Clinical picture and diagnostics. A patient with hypothyroidism can be encountered in the practice of a doctor of any profile. Moreover, the diagnosis is often made late, even with severe symptoms; Most researchers point to the time frame for establishing the correct diagnosis from several months to 2–3 years or more from the onset of the disease and, accordingly, a later start of replacement therapy [27–29]. Undiagnosed hypothyroidism is a risk factor for the progression of existing cardiovascular diseases due to indirect hyperhomocysteinemia, dyslipidemia and endothelial dysfunction [30–32]. In this regard, it is extremely necessary to know the principles of diagnosis and treatment methods for the disease. The variety of clinical manifestations of hypothyroidism is due to a decrease in the concentration of thyroid hormones, as a result of which the main metabolic reactions are inhibited and, most importantly, oxidative processes, basal metabolism, thermogenesis slow down, the activity of various enzyme systems and general blood flow decreases. The accumulation of protein and fluid in tissues and serous cavities is caused by increased extravasation of plasma proteins and insufficient lymphatic drainage [2, 30, 33]. The main pathogenetic mechanism of symptoms of thyroid insufficiency is the development of so-called mucinous (mucosal) edema, which is caused by decreased clearance, increased

synthesis and accumulation of hydrophilic glycosaminoglycans in the intercellular substance of the dermis and other tissues [27, 29, 33].

Treatment of hypothyroidism. Currently, synthetic analogues of thyroid hormones are used to treat hypothyroidism. Since the discovery and synthesis of the physiological L-form of thyroxine, drugs of this class have fully confirmed their priority in the treatment of hypothyroidism. Today, levothyroxine (LT4) is one of the 10 most prescribed drugs in the world [20, 52]. Since the main amount of triiodothyronine (T3) is formed in the periphery from T4 by deiodination, due to its depot properties and conversion according to individual needs into the metabolically more active triiodothyronine, synthetic levothyroxine has become the drug of choice [2, 53]. Clinically, the depot effect is extremely important: with a single dose of L-Thyroxine, due to deiodination, a constant T3 concentration is maintained throughout the day, which allows you to take the drug once a day, avoiding sharp peaks in triiodothyronine activity. In contrast, taking T3 drugs is accompanied by the achievement of a peak non-physiological level, followed by a fairly rapid decrease [7, 54, 55]. The goal of replacement therapy for primary hypothyroidism is to achieve and maintain normal serum TSH concentrations (blood sampling is carried out before taking the daily dose of L-T4) [53, 56]. The initial dose of L-Thyroxine and the time to reach the full replacement dose are determined individually, taking into account the patient's age, body weight, comorbidities, especially cardiovascular diseases [20, 52, 56]. Eating reduces the absorption of levothyroxine, so the entire individually selected dose is taken in the morning on an empty stomach, optimally 60 minutes before meals. The absorption of levothyroxine may be reduced in case of simultaneous use of aluminum-containing antacids (antacids, sucralfate), iron-containing drugs and calcium-containing drugs. Therefore, L-Thyroxine should be taken at least 2 hours before taking these medications [56, 57]. When taken orally, about 70–80% of the dose of L-Thyroxine taken is absorbed (Table 3), if it is a sodium salt; absorption is reduced when using pure T4, after meals (1–20%) or very large doses. The peak absorption of the drug occurs between 30 and 60 minutes after administration; it is completely absorbed after 90 minutes. 24–48 hours after the start of treatment with L-Thyroxine, the metabolic effect becomes noticeable, and after 14 days the clinical symptoms of hypothyroidism become less clear [52, 54]. L-Thyroxine therapy can be initiated immediately with a full replacement dose or with a minimum dose with a gradual increase in dose until the target TSH level in the blood is achieved. Traditionally, in young patients without cardiovascular pathology, replacement therapy is initiated with a full dose of L-Thyroxine (without preliminary titration) at the rate of 1.6–1.8 mcg per 1 kg of body weight per day (on average 75–112 mcg/day for women, 125–200 mcg/day for men).

Some patients with hypothyroidism and obesity may require 20% higher doses. In obese patients, it is better to calculate the dose based on the ideal weight, which allows achieving a therapeutic effect and compensating for hypothyroidism [53, 55]. Full replacement therapy for hypothyroidism is prescribed on the first day after thyroidectomy when hypothyroidism is diagnosed during pregnancy [54, 56].

Conclusion. To summarize, it should be noted that, despite the well-known clinical picture, the diagnosis of hypothyroidism can cause significant difficulties, since the deficiency of thyroid hormones is masked by various diseases. The decisive condition for successful medical care for patients with hypothyroidism is the timely administration of replacement therapy, which is lifelong in most patients. Taking into account individual sensitivity, the presence of comorbid pathology of internal organs, and drug interactions makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of treatment of hypothyroidism, minimize possible side effects and improve patient compliance.

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Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

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Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

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